

Adsorption of Crystal Violet on Hydrrous Ferric Oxide. Part I

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Hydrrous ferric oxide, precipitated by excess, equivalent, and deficient amount of alkali, has been found to be a good adsorbent for the basic dye, Crystal violet. The adsorptive capacity for the basic dye is maximum in the case of hydrrous oxide precipitated by the excess amount of alkali and is considerably less for that by the deficient amount of alkali. Hydrrous oxide, being amphoteric, shows acidic character when precipitated by excess amount of alkali and basic, when precipitated by deficient amount of alkali. The adsorption increases with increase in concentration of the dye and with rise in temperature. Freundlich's equation is not applicable over the complete range of concentration. The adsorptive capacity of the gel decreases on ageing, probably due to decrease in surface area and loss of water.

Hydrrous ferric oxide is a basic mordant and forms lakes with Alizarin S.W., Congo red etc., which have been said to be adsorption complexes. Koganovski¹ studied the adsorption of Congo red by hydrrous ferric oxide gel and found the adsorption isotherm to be of Langmuir type and the adsorptive capacity of the hydrrous oxide to diminish on its dehydration. Sen², Yoe³, and Lockeman *et al.*⁴ investigated adsorption of eighteen different organic acids and compounds of varying molecular structures by this gel.

Ghosh *et al.*⁵ and Ghosh and Tiwari⁶ reported that the nature of hydrrous ferric and chromic oxide could appreciably be changed by varying the concentrations of the interacting solutions and the temperature of precipitation. This communication deals with the study of the adsorption of Crystal violet on hydrrous ferric oxide, prepared according to the method of Ghosh *et al.*⁵⁻⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

E. Merck sample of ferric chloride was dissolved in distilled water. Its iron and chloride contents were respectively estimated volumetrically and gravimetrically. Iron and chloride contents were found to be in the ratio of 1:3. The hydrrous oxides were precipitated by the addition of varying amounts of NaOH (E. Merck) solution to a known estimated volume of ferric chloride solution, as shown in Table I

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1. *Kolloid Zhur.*, 1944, 11, 237; Koganovski and Kulski, *J. Appl. Chem. USSR*, 1944, 17, 599.

2. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 525, 1840.

3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2785.

4. *Kolloid Z.*, 1911, 8, 273; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 83, 735.

5. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1952, supplement, 21A; this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 65.

6. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1954, 20A, 42; *Kolloid Z.* 1951, 124, 31, 1052, 129, 31.

These samples were repeatedly washed with distilled water by decantation till the supernatant liquid gave no test for chloride content. The sample C could not, however, be washed completely free of chloride ions due to increased peptisation on washing. These precipitated suspensions in distilled water were stored in Jena glass bottles.

TABLE I

Sample.	Amount of alkali used.	Temp.
A	10% Excess of alkali	26°
B	Equivalent alkali	26°
C	10% Deficient alkali	26°

The known volumes of the above fresh samples were boiled for 2 hours and left overnight to attain the room temperature. The samples were diluted to the same volume as that of the fresh samples and left over for a fortnight. These samples were designated as A', B', and C'. Twenty ml of the suspension was used to study the adsorptive capacity of the fresh and aged samples of hydrous ferric oxide for the Crystal violet. The weight of the adsorbent as ferric oxide was determined by drying 20 ml of the suspension in a crucible on a water bath and finally ignited in an electric furnace at 1000°. The adsorbent was repeatedly dried and cooled till a constant weight of the ferric oxide was obtained.

Due to peptising tendency of the hydrous oxide in presence of the dye as well as to the very fine particles of hydrous oxide suspended in the supernatant liquid, it was considered necessary to coagulate them by addition of an electrolyte. Thus, for the adsorption studies, a 20-ml portion of the suspension and a 10-ml portion of 0.2 M potassium sulphate solution were mixed in separate 100-ml flasks and to them 5 to 40 ml of 0.01% of Crystal violet solution was added. The solutions were quickly made to 100 ml and were well shaken. All mixing and shaking were occasionally carried out in a thermostat wherein it was kept at a constant temperature for attaining saturation. The supernatant liquids were taken out after definite intervals, centrifuged for 10 minutes, and the residual dye concentration was estimated colorimetrically by diluting 5 ml of centrifuged dye with 3 ml of sodium acetate and acetic-acid buffer of pH 5.0 and 22 ml of distilled water to make the total volume to 30 ml.

DISCUSSION

The quantitative experimental data on the measurements of adsorption of Crystal violet dye by samples A, B, and C of hydrous ferric oxide at 30° are plotted as adsorption isotherms in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively, between the amount of Crystal violet dye adsorbed per g. mole of the hydrous oxide (X/M) and the end concentration (C) in g. moles. The amount of the dye adsorbed per g. mole of the hydrous oxide increases with the increasing concentration of the dye and the complete equilibrium is attained within 3 hours of contact for sample A, 2 hours for sample B, and 1 hour for sample C. The adsorption isotherms for samples B and C are convex to the concentration axis and are sigmoid in nature⁷. In the case of sample A, the adsorption isotherm starts out to be convex with respect to the concentration axis and is one (type III) of the physical adsorption isotherm types represented by Reyersson and Cameron⁸ for the adsorption of bromine by silica gel.

7. Brunauer, "The Adsorption of Gases and Vapour. Part I. Physical Adsorption", Oxford Univ. Press, 1945, p. 150.

8. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 181.

FIG. 1. Samples A, and B (at 30°).

FIG. 2. Sample C (at 30°).

An interesting fact is observed in the adsorption isotherms that at the higher initial concentrations of the dye, there is a tendency of a break in the adsorption isotherm. Such breaks are usual in multilayer adsorption of gases on solid surfaces, but have been rarely observed in the case of solutions. Gyani⁹ has, however, reported similar breaks in the adsorption isotherms of some organic dyes by silica gel. It appears that the adsorption of the dye from its solution by solids closely resembles the adsorption of gas on solids,

⁹ J. Indian Chem. Soc., News Ed., 1950, 13, 1, 8.

In Fig. 3, the applicability of Freundlich's equation has been studied. The isotherms are applicable within the limited range of the concentration of the dye. Langmuir's equation does not hold valid in the case of samples A and B. The convex nature¹⁰ of the isotherm indicates that the heat of adsorption of Crystal violet is smaller than the heat of aggregation of the colloidal micelle¹¹.

FIG. 3 Isotherms for samples A—C (at 30°).

The isotherms for the aged samples are very similar to those obtained for the fresh samples. The equilibrium is attained, however, within one hour of contact and the adsorptive capacity is smaller than that of fresh sample in each case. Similar results¹² have been observed in the case of adsorption of various dyes, organic acids, and compounds by hydrous chromium oxide, ferric oxide, etc. The decrease in adsorptive capacity of aged samples is usually attributed to polymerisation, ring closure, aggregation of minute particles, etc., resulting in decrease in the specific surface with dehydration or loss of water.

The adsorptive capacities of different samples of hydrous ferric oxide for Crystal violet is seen to be in the following decreasing order: $A > B > C$.

It indicates that the adsorption of the dye depends on the character of the hydrous oxide which varies with the amount of alkali added. The hydrous oxide, precipitated by adding excess of alkali to ferric chloride solution, is more acidic than that obtained by adding deficit amount of the alkali. The hydrous oxide being amphoteric in character is acidic when precipitated by excess of alkali and is therefore a better adsorbent for basic dyes such as Crystal violet.

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